

Immune System

Disorders

Associated Disorders and Diseases

Neurodegenerative

Pharmaceutical

Nervous system

Depression

Vascular dementia

Dementia

Smoking

Cancer Diseases
Colorectal cancer

Eosinophilic
esophagitis

Uremia

Ulcerativ
colitis

AIDS

Alzheimer
disease

Crohn's
disease

Asthma